

Existential Perspectives on the Fear of Death

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Abstract: The fear of death is a central theme in existentialism, psychology, and theology, profoundly influencing human life. This article examines the fear of death from an existentialist perspective, incorporating the contributions of thinkers such as Kierkegaard, Heidegger, Sartre, Frankl, and Yalom. It also explores existential psychotherapy approaches and the role of spirituality in managing existential anxiety. Finally, the study discusses the impact of modern society on the perception of death, including distancing from death through technology and medical practices. The research highlights the importance of consciously confronting mortality to live an authentic and meaningful life.

Keywords: Fear of Death, Existential Anxiety, Existential Psychotherapy, Viktor Frankl, Irvin Yalom, Death and Spirituality, Existentialist Philosophy, Modern Society and Death

Introduction

Throughout history, death has been perceived as an inevitable and omnipresent phenomenon, an integral part of human existence. As Ariès (1974, p. 85) observes, "death, once so omnipresent that it was familiar, would be erased, would disappear. It would become shameful and forbidden." This shift in the way modern society relates to death has had a profound impact on the human psyche, generating heightened existential anxiety. Fromm (1956, p. 8) asserts that "certainty exists only with respect to the past—and regarding the future, the only certainty is death." He also draws attention to the routine that dominates modern life, contributing to the neglect of one's own mortality: "From birth to death, from Monday to Monday, from morning to evening, all activities are routinized and prefabricated. How can a man caught in this web of routine avoid forgetting that he is a man, a unique individual, who has been given but one chance to live—with hopes and disappointments, with sadness and fear, with the desire for love and the horror of nothingness and separation" (Fromm, 1956, p. 17)?

According to Solomon, Greenberg, and Pyszczynski (2015, pp. 25-26), the fear of death begins manifesting in early childhood: "There is evidence suggesting that by as early as three years of age, children are aware of death and, because they are uncomfortable with it, begin to employ rudimentary versions of the terror management strategies they will later rely on as adults." The diversion strategies used by both children and adults include distracting themselves through trivial activities, ignoring the awareness of their own mortality, and taking refuge in a routinized life.

Existential Anxiety and the Fear of Death: Philosophical Perspectives

The fear of death in existentialist thought is deeply connected to the contributions of philosophers such as Søren Kierkegaard, Martin Heidegger, Jean-Paul Sartre, Viktor Frankl, and others. Kierkegaard (1980) was among the first to explore the concept of existential anxiety, describing it as the "dizziness of freedom," a state inherent to the awareness of one's finite existence (p. 61). Heidegger (2003) develops the concept of "being-toward-death" (p. 615), arguing that "from the moment of birth, man is old enough to die" (p. 327). Sartre asserts that "man is condemned to be free," which implies radical responsibility for one's own life and for the way one confronts the fear of death (p. 101). "Whether we like it or not, we are free and therefore absolutely responsible for what we do" (Spade, 2010, pp. 101, 117). Frankl (1992), from a logotherapeutic perspective, suggests that the meaning of life is the key to overcoming existential anxiety: "It does not really matter what we expect from life, but rather what life expects from us" (p. 85).

Epicurus presents a different view, asserting that death should not be feared: "when we exist, death is not, and when death is, we no longer exist." In this way, he presents the moment of transition from life to death as a point at which these two forces never meet and never confront one another, since in the presence of one, the other is absent, and vice versa. (...) Thus, the subject of death holds absolutely no significance either for the living—because, through the presence of their senses, they defy death—or for the dead, because, in the absence of senses, they cannot perceive what it means to be dead. For this reason, a wise man exists without fear. A wise man lives, feels, and dies without regrets” (Anastasiadou, 2017–2018, pp. 5–6).

Tillich states that "anxiety is the existential awareness of nonbeing" and explains: “The term ‘existential’ in this sentence means that it is not about an abstract knowledge of nonbeing, but about the awareness that nonbeing is part of one’s very being. It is not about the realization of universal transience, nor even about the experience of the death of others, but about the impression these events have on the latent awareness of our own inevitable death, which generates anxiety” (Tillich, 1952, p. 35). Van Deurzen (2012, p. 48) argues: "The courage to live can only be found when the possibility of death is faced with determination" Echoing this, Jonas (1984, p. 46) adds that "the sacrifice of one's own life for the salvation of others, for one’s country, or for a humanitarian cause represents a choice in favor of being, not of nonbeing"

Facing death can be a source of meaning. Moody (1975, p. 156) emphasizes the impact that reflections on death have on the way we live our lives: "What we learn about death can have a significant impact on how we live our lives." Michel de Montaigne, in his essays, proposes a rational approach to death: "To learn how to philosophize is to learn how to die" (Montaigne, 1993, p. 128). This perspective suggests that accepting death is an essential part of both philosophical and psychological development. Camus (1972, p. 75) even states that "death is merely an accident of happiness" and that it has nothing to do with happiness. Van Deurzen further deepens the existential perspective, arguing that the true challenge of life is not death itself, but the awareness of its inevitability. In this perspective, she introduces the concept of self-deception, showing that, “Self-deception, through which we ignore weakness, limitations, and death, is not based on the fear of death but on the fear of life. Accepting death is often easier than we expect; the true challenge is to be aware of its inevitability and yet move forward. The true struggle of life lies in the creative use of this paradox, and self-affirmation and the full experience of life can only arise from confronting the inevitability of one's own death” (Van Deurzen, 2012, p. 29). This approach suggests that life gains meaning not by avoiding death, but by integrating the awareness of it into our daily existence. Ultimately, the acceptance of one's own mortality is not a surrender, but the first step toward a life truly lived. How we choose to relate to this defining reality of our being determines the depth and authenticity with which we live.

The Existential Psychotherapeutic Approach

While existentialist philosophy emphasizes the inevitability of anxiety related to death, existential psychotherapy offers a practical framework through which individuals can learn to manage this inevitable reality. This therapeutic approach does not seek to eliminate the fear of death, but rather to help people integrate it in a way that enables them to live a more authentic and committed life.

May, one of the central figures of existential psychotherapy, considers that the fear of death has a profound impact on human consciousness and behavior. In his foundational work *Existential Psychotherapy*, May (1975) analyzes how existential anxiety influences an individual's life and creativity. He emphasizes that many people react to this fear through conformity, leading to a mechanical existence devoid of authenticity. In this regard, May describes conformity as "a real partial death even though one's body continues to live. It is the loss of consciousness of self, the loss of your potentialities and sensibilities, the loss of what

characterizes you or me as unique and original beings. By this means, we temporarily escape death anxiety, 'nonbeing,' but it exacts the price of forfeiting life" (May, 1975, p. 56).

According to May, the acceptance of the mortal condition should not be seen as a source of despair, but as a gateway to authenticity. He asserts that "creativity arises out of the courageous confrontation with death and not out of the denial of death" (May, 1975, p. 54). In this way, the acknowledgment of one's mortality can become a transformative impulse for assuming personal responsibilities and creating one's own meaning of existence.

Another significant contributor to the existential perspective on the fear of death is psychiatrist and author Irvin D. Yalom. In his works, *Existential Psychotherapy*, *Staring at the Sun*, and *Love's Executioner and Other Tales of Psychotherapy*, Yalom explores how the awareness of death influences the human psyche. He argues that "death is the condition that makes life possible" (Yalom, 2010, p. 45) and that death anxiety represents "the background music of life" (Yalom, 2008, p. 11). This anxiety is omnipresent, subtly influencing each individual's decisions and perspectives. Moreover, Yalom considers that "the awareness of death can serve as a revealing experience, as an extremely useful catalyst for significant life course changes" (Yalom, 2008, p. 30). Thus, instead of paralyzing the individual, confronting death can motivate one to make more authentic decisions and to reorganize one's priorities. He also emphasizes the role of authentic interpersonal relationships, stating that "those who have a tendency to move continuously and authentically toward others, because their inner world is full, will experience a softening of existential anxiety" (Yalom, 2010, p. 460). In this way, social support and genuine human connections can play a crucial role in managing existential anxiety.

In this context, the fear of death is not merely a source of suffering but also a "motor" for personal transformation. Ernest Becker argues that "the idea of death, the fear of it, haunts the human animal like nothing else; it is the mainspring of human activity—activity designed largely to avoid the fatality of death, to overcome it by denying in some way that it is the final destiny for man" (Becker, 1973, p. ix). This point of view highlights the fact that many of humanity's cultural, scientific, and artistic achievements are, in essence, attempts to transcend the mortal condition. Near-death experiences offer a unique perspective on this phenomenon. Forsyth and Eifert (2007) emphasize: "We know from testimonies that something profound happens when people have come close to the brink between life and death and have survived to live another day. Their lives change dramatically. Confronting death forces people to take stock. And when they do, many end up radically changing what they were doing and begin to spend more time engaging in activities that truly matter to them. Old habits and activities that once seemed so important become trivial. In short, contact with the brink between life and death awakens people. Something is triggered. People change what they do and how they live in ways that are richer, more vital, and more meaningful than before. They choose to spend the remaining time on this planet doing things that matter" (Forsyth & Eifert, 2007, p. 100). Thus, we observe that limit experiences, direct confrontations with death, can have a profound impact, prompting individuals to reevaluate the way they live their lives.

DeSpelder and Strickland also analyze how near-death experiences can transform one's perspective on existence. They argue that individuals who have undergone such experiences become more aware of life's fragility and develop a deeper commitment to their authentic values. They display "an increased appreciation for life and a stronger determination to make better use of the opportunities presented to them. They become more confident in their abilities and better able to manage life's difficulties. Interpersonal relationships gain greater importance, while material comfort becomes less relevant." Researcher Kenneth Ring, who specializes in the study of near-death experiences, states that the typical individual who has undergone such an experience "has acquired a sense of what is important in life and strives to live in accordance with their understanding of what truly matters" (DeSpelder & Strickland, 2020, p. 536).

In this sense, Emmy van Deurzen presents the existentialist approach as follows: “An existentialist attitude always involves the direct confrontation with what appears negative and difficult in order to discover its positive implications... When life is no longer taken for granted, existential anxiety becomes inevitable. However, when anxiety is repressed, it is replaced by despair as we realize the exhausting impossibility of existence. (...) The courage to live can only be found when the possibility of death is faced with determination. Existential therapy aims to help people discover this courage by encouraging them to bring all their anxieties to the surface and to face life directly, without avoidance. Anxiety provides all the energy necessary to assume our responsibilities” (Van Deurzen, 2012, p. 48).

Thus, the acceptance and exploration of the fear of death are essential for living an authentic, fulfilling, and conscious life. As we strive to find meaning in our lives, the confrontation with the reality of mortality becomes inevitable. Although the fear of death can be a powerful catalyst for human activity and the pursuit of authenticity, over time this fear transforms into a direct confrontation with the inherent losses of aging and the approach of death. Ultimately, these losses—whether physical, social, or emotional—emphasize the inevitability of the end and challenge us to rethink how we relate to our existential freedom.

Confronting One’s Own Mortality and the Aging Process

While existential psychotherapy offers methods through which individuals can manage death-related anxiety, helping them to find meaning and assume responsibility for their own existence, the process of aging brings this confrontation into a more concrete and profoundly personal dimension. As the years pass, the prospect of the end becomes increasingly tangible, prompting individuals to reevaluate their priorities and how they perceive their existence. Thus, old age should not be viewed merely as a physical decline but also as a stage of psychological adjustment to the reality of existential limits and the approach of death.

Death, as emphasized by Mitchell and Anderson, has always been perceived as a unique, absolute, and final event that cannot be reduced merely to the idea of a simple loss. In this sense, they state that “it has been and always will be completely special, absolute, and final, (...) it is not ‘just another form of loss!’” (Bregman, 2011, p. 157). However, as people age, they face a continuous process of loss, both physically and psychosocially. Dunlop describes this reality in his book *Finishing Well to the Glory of God*, where he explains: “As we age, we will inevitably face losses. After all, much of what we experience in the later years of life involves loss. Vernon Grounds, dean emeritus of Western Seminary in Denver, spoke of the “constraints of age” upon reaching the age of 87. He grouped the losses caused by aging into less space and less time. The days of international travel were gone; now his life was confined to a single building. Space was limited. Time was also limited: he could no longer make long-term plans because he was aware that death could come at any moment” (Dunlop, 2011, pp. 25–26).

This progressive narrowing of experiences brings the individual face to face with two essential realities:

- “The certainty of death. Death is inevitable. Man is born to die. Nature shows him that the end will come.
- The nearness of death. Man must die soon. How soon, he cannot tell.” (Ketcham, 1899, p. 20)

The awareness of these two realities prompts individuals to reevaluate their lives, reconsider their priorities, and reflect on how they choose to live the remaining years of their existence. In this context, Becker, in his renowned work *The Denial of Death*, raises a fundamental question: “If we come from nothing and return to nothing, how can we avoid even now a sense of nothingness?”

For Yalom (2008, p. 14), the inevitability of death can be perceived as a factor that undermines any meaning in life. He states that “the inevitability of death makes all life

meaningless." However, the solution proposed by Yalom is not the denial of this truth but the adoption of an existentialist perspective: "For me personally, and in my psychotherapy practice, the most effective approach to death anxiety is the existential one" (Yalom, 2008, p. 118). Thus, within the framework of existential psychotherapy, therapists support patients in the process of exploring their own values, goals, and interpersonal relationships, helping them to take responsibility for their lives and to find a personal sense of meaning. This approach does not eliminate the fear of death but encourages patients to accept and integrate it into their existence, so they may live with authenticity and courage.

However, the existential psychotherapeutic approach operates outside the framework of any religion, as its principles are often incompatible with the theological view of life and death. This conflict is evident in the response Yalom gave to a rabbi (whom he perceived as a disguised missionary) who attempted to merge religious beliefs with existentialist principles: "There is a fundamental antagonism between our points of view. Your belief in a personal, omnipresent, and all-knowing God who protects you and offers you a life plan is incompatible with the foundation of my existential view of humanity as free, mortal, and thrown alone and at random into an indifferent universe. In your view, death is not the end. You tell me that death is only a night between two days and that the soul is immortal. So yes, there is indeed a problem with your desire to become an existential therapist: our points of view are diametrically opposed" (Yalom, 2010, p. 158). This perspective highlights a fundamental difference between the religious and existential approaches to death: while the former offers a transcendent vision based on the hope of an afterlife, the latter insists on the acceptance of the finite reality of human existence.

Regarding the management of existential anxiety, Yalom emphasizes the importance of human connections, stating that: "We human beings are all programmed to connect with others. (...) Intimate relationships are a sine qua non for happiness," and "loneliness greatly amplifies death anxiety" (Yalom, 2008, p. 119–120). Thus, beyond the attempt to face the fear of death individually, people can find comfort and meaning through authentic relationships with others. Existential therapy thus becomes a powerful tool for transforming death-related anxiety into a motivating force for living a more conscious, authentic, and meaningful life.

Spirituality and the Fear of Death

In the context of the search for meaning in the face of death, Viktor Frankl offers a profound perspective that emphasizes the individual's responsibility toward their own existence. He suggests that instead of asking what the meaning of life is, we should see ourselves as being questioned by existence itself, with each moment bringing a new challenge. Thus, Frankl (1992, p. 85) argues that the meaning of life should not be sought through abstract reflections or theoretical discussions, but must be discovered through our daily actions and choices. He states that our answers must be expressed through "right actions and appropriate conduct." Furthermore, he raises a fundamental rhetorical question: "Does not the final meaning of life, if it is ever revealed, reveal itself only at its end, on the verge of death?" (Frankl, 1992, p. 145). This profound question suggests that the true meaning of life may be fully understood only when we are confronted with our imminent end, a moment that compels us to reflect upon our entire existence. Frankl's perspective stands in contrast to the approach of Yalom, who views the fear of death as a fundamental element of the human condition, but does not consider it necessary to anchor this fear in a spiritual dimension. Unlike Frankl, Yalom believes that the individual must find meaning within the limits of material and finite reality, without relying on a transcendent hope. Although Yalom views religion as a human construct, he does not deny that it plays an important role in how people manage their fear of death. Religion, in many cultures, has functioned as a mechanism for alleviating existential anxiety by providing answers to the great questions about death and the afterlife. Yalom acknowledges that religion not only offers a sense of security in the face of death but also provides a framework through which people can live a

meaningful life. This view becomes evident in his psychotherapeutic practice, where, despite his secular stance, he states: "When working with a religious person, I follow the principle that stands at the top of my hierarchy of values: concern for my patients" (Yalom, 2008, p. 5), emphasizing his respect for his patients' beliefs even if his own perspective is different.

Thus, Yalom demonstrates respect for his patients' beliefs, even though his own convictions differ. Furthermore, Yalom highlights the essential role of religion in humanity's construction of an understanding of death: "Death anxiety is the mother of all religions, which, in one way or another, attempt to temper the angst of our finitude. God, as transculturally formulated, not only soothes the pain of mortality through the vision of an eternal life but also alleviates terrifying isolation by offering an eternal presence, and furthermore, provides a model for living a meaningful life" (Yalom, 2008, p. 5).

In contrast to this view, theologian Ratzinger (1988, p. 214) asserts that in the search for meaning, man can find a satisfactory answer only in Jesus Christ, the sole authentic source of hope and eternal life. He declares: "The risen Jesus is our guarantee that history can be lived positively and that our rational, limited, and weak activity has meaning." Thus, we see a clear difference between these three perspectives on the meaning of life in the face of death. Frankl insists that a person can discover authentic meaning only through a personal spiritual dimension, without necessarily anchoring it in an institutionalized religion. In contrast, Yalom remains committed to a secular existentialist approach, considering that meaning must be constructed within the limits of finite reality. On the other hand, the theological perspective advocated by Ratzinger proposes a definitive solution through faith in Christ and the promise of eternal life. These varied approaches reflect the complexity of how people relate to death and highlight the fact that the meaning of existence is deeply influenced by individual beliefs and values.

Modern Society and the Distancing from Death

In contemporary society, the perception of death has changed significantly as medical technology has advanced and taken on a central role in prolonging life. Kübler-Ross (2014, p. 18) observed that we live "in a society where more and more people are 'kept alive' both with the help of machines that replace vital organs and with computers that periodically check whether additional physiological functions need to be replaced by electronic equipment." This dependence on technology not only prolongs life but also distances individuals from the reality of death, transforming it into a mechanized process removed from the everyday sphere.

Yalom (2008) emphasizes that "each historical era develops its own methods of dealing with death" (p. 117), indicating that, regardless of scientific progress, existential anxiety remains a human constant. In today's society, this anxiety has not disappeared but has been transformed through different mechanisms, such as the excessive medicalization of death or a culture of denial that hides the reality of the end within hospitals and nursing homes. Death is increasingly perceived as an isolated, mechanized, and dehumanizing event. The dying are removed from their familiar environments and placed into medical institutions, where the process of dying is dominated by technological interventions and standardized protocols. Kemp (2019) emphasizes that "although many people imagine they will die at home, surrounded by loved ones, in reality, more than six out of ten of us will die in an institutional setting, such as a hospital or nursing home" (p. 25). Keller (2017, p. 7) similarly argues that "modern medicine has hidden death from us," separating it from everyday life and transforming it into a sterilized event.

In hospitals, patients are often treated without being given the opportunity to express their views or wishes regarding the end of life. Kübler-Ross (1969) draws attention to this issue, stating that when "a patient is gravely ill, he is often treated as a person without the right to an opinion. (...) It would take so little to remember that the ill person also has feelings, desires, and opinions, and, most importantly, has the right to be heard" (p. 13). Unfortunately,

medical education contributes to this trend, maintaining an overly technical and insufficiently humanistic approach. Chiou, Tsai, and Han (2023 p. 5) emphasize that "today's medical education is filled with excessively technical and non-humanistic training, favoring curing over caring [for the soul]."

While medical technology offers the possibility of prolonging life, it also raises complex ethical issues. Fiddes (n.d.) highlights the ambiguity of this reality, stating that "although we are all aware of the indignity endured by people when physicians heroically strive to keep them alive with infusions, intravenous tubes, and ventilators, sometimes those who have survived express satisfaction at the extension of their lives" (p. 10). This dilemma reflects the conflict between the desire to live longer and the suffering caused by unnecessary prolongation.

Gawande (2015) observes that patients with serious illnesses do not merely wish to extend their lives but have other priorities as well: "People with serious illness have priorities besides simply prolonging their lives. Surveys have shown that their top concerns are to avoid suffering, to strengthen their relationships with family and friends, to maintain mental clarity, to not be a burden to others, and to achieve a sense of completion in life" (p. 129). Malysz (n.d. pp. 9–10) also argues that "the most precious of human values, the sine qua non attribute of humanity, is a life lived with dignity; not survival at any cost. (...) [Dignity] confers upon life its human dimension."

The fundamental question that arises is whether modern science truly addresses the deepest human needs, which have remained unchanged over time. Kübler-Ross emphasizes that medicine should remain a humanitarian profession, focused on alleviating suffering and not merely on prolonging life at all costs. She observes that gravely ill patients are often subjected to invasive and prolonged treatments, with the medical team prioritizing the maintenance of life even when it becomes futile: "The patient may wish to fight against everyone, but it will be a futile fight, because everything is being done in the fight for his life, and if they (the medical team) can save his life, they can think about the person afterward. (...) Are we becoming less human or more human? (...) It is clear that, regardless of the answer, the patient suffers more—not physically, perhaps, but emotionally. And his needs have not changed over the centuries, only our ability to meet them. (...) Should medicine remain a humanitarian and respected profession, or should it become a new depersonalized science serving the prolongation of life rather than the alleviation of human suffering?" (Kübler-Ross, 1969, pp. 14–15).

This tendency is also supported by a study conducted on medical students, which shows that when reminded of their own mortality, they tend to favor the prolongation of life for a gravely ill patient, even if this decision goes against the expressed wishes of the patient (Solomon, Greenberg & Pyszczynski, 2015, p. 157). Gawande (2015, p. 129) also emphasizes the failure of the modern medical system to respect patients' wishes, observing that "our technology-driven medical system has utterly failed to meet these aims" and raising the crucial question: "How do we build a health care system that actually helps people achieve what's most important to them at the end of their lives?"

To address this issue, Ezekiel and Linda Emanuel propose the model of "shared decision-making," which allows patients to express their concerns and wishes regarding their own medical care. The physician does not make decisions unilaterally but instead asks patients directly about their priorities: "What is most important to you? What are your concerns?" and informs them about the options available to achieve their goals (Gawande, 2015, pp. 166–167). This paradigm shift is also supported by Sârbu (2020), who argues that "decisions should not focus solely on death or the dying process, but on the quality of life and the prevention of any possible abuse" (p. 765).

Another problematic aspect is the way modern society perceives death. Lucy Bregman (2011) criticizes the expression "lost the battle against cancer," stating that it reflects a mentality that

associates death with personal failure. She argues that this approach stems from a denial of the reality of death, which can lead patients to undergo additional unnecessary and painful treatments (p. 159). Giorgio Agamben also analyzes this tendency of late modernity to reduce human life to its mere biological existence, asserting that: "The Human Genome Project, the global economy, and the humanitarian ideology are all dedicated to maintaining mere biological life, whose "well-being seems to be the final historical task of humanity" (Malysz, n.d., p. 10). The obsession with prolonging life at the expense of the patient's dignity has created a deep rift between human needs and the medical system. Kübler-Ross (1969, p. 15) warns about this phenomenon and emphasizes that medicine must remain a profession focused on the patient's well-being, not merely on the artificial prolongation of life: "Medicine must remain a humanitarian and respected profession or become a new depersonalized science in the service of prolonging life rather than alleviating human suffering."

Based on these findings, it is essential for medical education to evolve toward a more empathetic approach, where the ultimate goal is not merely the extension of life but also the alleviation of suffering and the respect for the patient's dignity. The "shared decision-making" model can offer a solution for rehumanizing medical care and ensuring that patients are not treated merely as biological objects but as human beings whose emotional and spiritual needs must be considered.

Conclusion

Death remains one of the deepest themes of human reflection, perceived either as an existential threat or as an opportunity for the reevaluation of life and personal values. The philosophical and psychotherapeutic perspectives analyzed in this article demonstrate the complexity of the fear of death and its impact on the human psyche. From the existentialist approaches of Heidegger, Sartre, and Frankl to the psychotherapeutic theories of May and Yalom, the idea emerges that the acceptance of one's own mortality can become a source of authenticity and meaning.

In contrast, modern society has developed mechanisms to avoid confrontation with death, including excessive medicalization, the concealment of the dying process within specialized institutions, and a culture that tends to deny the finality of human existence. This trend raises ethical and existential concerns, as Kübler-Ross emphasizes, with medicine risking becoming a depersonalized science focused solely on prolonging life without considering its quality.

In the face of these challenges, existentialist therapeutic models propose alternatives that do not deny the fear of death but encourage its constructive integration. Authentic human connections, the assumption of responsibility for one's own life, and the cultivation of a personal sense of meaning are essential factors in overcoming existential anxiety. Furthermore, the spiritual dimension plays a crucial role in how individuals relate to death, offering different responses according to personal beliefs.

Ultimately, the exploration of the fear of death is not merely a theoretical exercise but a necessity for authentic existence. As Frankl suggests, the meaning of life often takes shape in moments of confrontation with our fundamental limitations. The acceptance of mortality should not be seen as a source of despair but as an invitation to live a more conscious and meaningful life.

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